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Information Misuse in an Era of New Media Technologies: Perceived Roles of Libraries and Librarians

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Abstract

In this era of new media technologies where access to and distribution of information have become very easy, it has been noticed that this development has brought about increase in the spread of malicious and harmful information product which tend to pose a threat to the society. This study therefore took a look at the perceived roles of librarians in fight this cankerworm called information misuse in an era of new technologies. The study which was guided by six research questions employed a descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 420 librarians purposively selected among librarians in Nigeria. The principle instrument used for data collection is the questionnaire structured according to a modified Likert scale on four point rating scale. while the data collected were analyzed using frequency and simple percentile and presented in tables. The outcome of the study shows that information misuse do come in the forms of misinformation, malign-information, disinformation, hoaxes, propaganda, and fake news etc and mostly created by politicians and other individuals for different selfish purposes at the detriment of the wider society. The study further discovered that various new media are used to promote information misuse whose effects include among others; erosion of trust among the people, manipulation of public opinions, weakening democratic established institutions and polarization of the society, In this case, it was established that libraries and librarians can help curb this societal menace by engaging on enlightenment campaigns, leading digital literacy, teaching fact-checking techniques and collaboration with other professional bodies. It was based on the findings that it was recommended among other things that libraries and librarians should occupy the drivers' seats as information mediators and directors with a view to winning public confidence through the provision and dissemination of accurate and reliable information and that

Libraries' management should as a matter of necessity train every staff on cyber and data security as a general corporate policy.

Keywords: Information, Information Misuse, Society, Library, Librarians, new media, Misinformation,

1.0. Introduction

In recent time, information which is seen as the communication of news and knowledge and that which helps to reduce uncertainty and assist us in decision making (Onwubiko,2016), has become the greatest asset of any nation and the first among all factors of production. This is because a well informed society stands out in the mist of others as it stands ahead in development. On the other hand, information like fire may also turn a bad servant and consume the society if not appropriately applied. Stating the obvious, to many people, Information means many things that it may be compare with the story of the seven blind men and the elephant depending on the context and for this reason, depending on the understanding and intent it may applied to achieve good, bad or the ugly. As explained by deWatteville and Gilbert (2000), information is any potentially useful fact, quantity or value that can be expressed uniquely with exactness. While in the views of Womboh and Abba (2008) it is processed data that aids decision making. It could also be visualized as a commodity that could be bought or sold. In this study, information is anything that we come in contact with directly or indirectly that adds to our knowledge and is capable of causing a human mind to change its opinion about the current state of the real world, and in a library, information is data that have been processed into form that is meaningful to the recipient/user and is of real or perceived value in current and future decision.

We are in era which has been transformed by the emergence of information and communication technologies (ICTs) with information growing exponentially. . This transformation further made information dissemination and accessibility very easy more so through the new media technologies.. New media technologies often referred to as Web 2.0- encompass a wide variety of web-related communication technologies, such as blogs, wikis, online social networking, virtual worlds and other social media forms (Friedman & Friedman, 2008). The new media unlike the old media (television, newspapers, magazines, radio, etc) are flexible channels for content creation and dissemination.. Availability and accessibility of these pieces of information

has given rise to a wave of concern, if not a threat to the continued existence of the society around the globe. This quantum of information at the finger tips of the public has been misused for many reasons, but particularly for self interest.

Information misuse connotes the unethical use of information usually with the intention to manipulate, mislead or cause harm to an individual, group or an organisation. It is an intentional or deliberate distortion or misrepresentation of a factual content with the aim of achieving predetermined outcome. Santos-D'amorim and Miranda (2021) associated misused concepts of misinformation, disinformation and mal-information to words such as; bias, propaganda, retracted papers, conspiracy theories, misleading representation in maps, charts and graphics, fake news, click bait, hoax, satire or parody, imposter website, fake reviews, phishing, filter bubbles, and echo chambers.

In the last few years, false and misleading information has caused or contributed to a wide range of harm to individuals and groups across the world from vigilante violence unrest and civil unrest in Ethiopia; Nigeria as seen during the 2023 Presidential elections, DR. Congo, Mali, war in Sudan, Ukraine etc.. Information which is originally meant to enlighten and to dispel ignorance leading to well mannered and well behaved society has been bastardized and now being used as a weapon of mass destruction in our society (Cunliffe-Jones, et al. 2021)..

To this end, the global system has so much be bastardized that most things have fallen apart and the center can no more hold resulting to bad government, bad economy, and climate change among others that have given rise to the uncontrollable misuse of information. The internet which is the greatest technology of our time and the most innovative technology that has appeared in the last 20 years did make the world a global village that information misuse sweeps like a wild fire that destroys the good vegetations. .

Be that as it may, on the face of unrelated peddling of fake news in our society, it is difficult for the public to filter, refine and select what they receive (Santin & Pra, 2021). The ability of the populace to filter through the ubiquitous generated content which comes in form of text, pictures, graphics, videos and the likes is equally as important as the quality of decision they will make.

Information as a product is the oil that lubricates the joints that keeps modern society working and the growth therein. However, it must be used rightly. By misrepresenting reality with traces of truth, there is a distortion of entire collective imaginary and manipulation of public opinion which in turn leads to major problems politically, socially and economically (Satin & Pra, 2021). Evidence has shown that the situation of information misuse has worsened as a result of contemporary new media. In fact the assertion is that information misuse has gained prominence through social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, Google, YouTube, and other social media platforms.

New media technology is any type of application meant to transfer information via digital techniques, computerized systems or data networks. First established in the 20th century, this technology is most readily associated with information transfers meant to be manipulated in some way. Most forms are interactive and contain compressed data designed to be accessed in a variety of markets (Chavis, 2023). This technology has indeed led to cultural globalization in that we can now interact with others on a global level and form connections virtually, rather than locally. These wider networks enable ‘collective intelligence’ in that they allow people to share and combine resources, data, skills, and information for any given purpose. New media presents a very different reality than our everyday, face-to-face reality. Against this backdrop, the researcher felt that there is need for a social institution like the library and professionals who are effective in managing information (Librarians) to come to the rescue. This is built on the assertion that the exponential growth of information fuelled by the exploitation of media such as the web and social networking, demands that there be a mediator with the skills and capacity to extract trusted and authentic information. Such an intermediary also has to be able to deliver reliable and authoritative information to the information-seeking community as well as the new knowledge and information that has been created in recent times (Tise ,2011),.

This study therefore takes a look at how libraries and librarians through their roles can contribute in fighting this societal mess called information misuse as well as creating that awareness of the danger of information misuse and the way forward.

. Research Objectives

The primary objective of this study was to ascertain the roles of libraries and librarian in fighting information misuse in an era of new media technologies. Other objectives were:

1. To ascertain the forms information misuse are depicted
2. To identify those involved in information misuse
3. To ascertain the Reasons behind information misuse
4. To establish the new media that are used to peddle misinformation
5. To discover the consequences of information misuse
6. To establish the perceived Roles of Libraries and Librarians in the fight against information misuse

To realize the above objectives, the study was guided by six research questions.

1. In what Forms are information misuse depicted?
2. Who are those involved in information misuse?
3. What are the Reasons behind information misuse?
4. What new media are used to peddle misinformation?
5. What are the Consequences of information misuse?
6. What Roles are Libraries and Librarians expected to play in the fight against information misuse?

2.0. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Conceptual Framework

The Web 2.0 Perspective

To many the term Web 2.0 refers to the technological underpinnings of much of what we call new media. This term probably came into usage around 2001, when O'Reilly Publications started to refer to "modern" Internet applications as "Web 2.0" The implication is that these are second generation web applications, a quantum leap ahead of the old applications (Vossen and Hagemann 2007); the idea being that, say, a personal web page is Web 1.0; a blog is Web 2.0. One interesting feature in this perspective is that of control. Web 1.0 applications were intended to force people to do certain things in certain ways at particular locations. With Web 2.0, the

technology empowers users and this far from stifling web-related activities; actually stimulates innovation and growth.

New Media

As a member of an increasingly globalized, technologically advanced world, you probably use new media every day to stay in touch with your loved ones, discover and engage in your interests, and keep up with the news. You may use it to study for school and you might work remotely once you graduate. Whether it's our educations, careers, hobbies, or personal lives; life in contemporary society is almost invariably shaped by media, particularly new media..

In fact, the term new media is used ubiquitously in many different ways. For instance, Lievrouw and Livingstone (2002) focus on the message (i.e., the communication and its practices), the technology (i.e., the medium), and the social context in which it is used. These three aspects of the new media show up repeatedly in the literature along with other more specific technologies and practices such as collaboration, digitization, and telecommunication. Gitelman and Pingree (2003) take the temporal approach, using the term "media in transition" to describe a period of time during which a medium is emergent and thus a sort of contrast to and competitor for the old media.

As explained, new media doesn't necessarily refer to a specific mode of communication. Some types of new media, such as an online newspaper, are also "old media" in the form of a traditional printed newspaper. Other new media are entirely new, such as a podcast or smartphone app. It becomes even more complicated to define when you consider that as technology continues to advance, the definition continually changes. New media is any media—from newspaper articles and blogs to music and podcasts; that are delivered digitally. From a website or email to mobile phones and streaming apps, any internet-related form of communication can be considered new media (Cote, 2022). While the New Media Institute (n.d) defines new media as a catchall term used to define all that is related to the internet and the interplay between technology, images and sound. That is in contrast to "old media," which PCMag (n.d) defines as all forms of communication that came before digital technology, including "radio and TV and printed materials such as books and magazines. As noted, it also

constantly changes. As new technology is developed and widely adopted, what is considered new continues to morph. Once upon a time, DVDs and CDs were the latest way to watch movies and listen to music. Now, streaming services such as Netflix and Spotify are more popular. Few examples new media as listed by the institute include: Blogs; Email, Music and television streaming services, Social media networks, Virtual and augmented reality and Websites. One can therefore deduce that new media is a term that encompasses two trends that have occurred over the past few decades: the evolution of existing media delivery systems and the development of new digital communication technologies which include: Websites; Social media networks such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat and TikTok, Email, Blogs and Music, film and television streaming services such as Netflix, Hulu, Amazon Prime Video and Disney+ among many others..

New Media Technology

New media technology is any type of application meant to transfer information via digital techniques, computerized systems or data networks. First established in the 20th century, this technology is most readily associated with information transfers meant to be manipulated in some way. Most forms are interactive and contain compressed data designed to be accessed in a variety of markets (Chavis, 2023). The most prevalent examples of new media include Internet-based concepts, like websites, or digital mediums, such as CD-ROMs and DVDs. Anything that is considered old media, such as television, film or paper-based products, are not part of new media (Chavis, 2023). The concept got its start in the 1960s. With the rise of modern computer technology, the idea of information exchange through the medium became a powerful application. Artists and designers used this technology to bring new concepts to fruition, creating things like digital-based artwork and video games. These technologies became highly prevalent in the 1980s, slowly replacing traditionally mediums, primarily through the implementation of personal computers and video game systems. This was also supported by desktop publishing methods that allowed for easier image manipulation techniques and online publications.

According to new media technology standards, certain commonalities exist between all types of modern mediums. Geographic distance is compromised due to the fact that the technology can be used in nearly every market around the world. The level and speed of communication is

increased because of the Internet. Additionally, the interactive level of information exchange allows users to adapt to new methodologies while supplying their own input. Also, previously isolated forms of communication, such as video and telephony, can be merged together.

Information Misuse

In a simple parlance information also called data misuse is using any information in a way it's not supposed to be used as terms of proper data use are usually spelled out in laws, industry standards, corporate policies, and user agreements. Information misuse is also seen as the inappropriate use of data as defined when the data was initially collected. Basically, it's when data is not used the way it's initially intended to be used ([Sai Chavali, 2018](#)). Information misuse comes in different forms which include; misinformation; mal-information, fake news, propaganda, conspiracy theory, rumors and hoax, disinformation and manipulated media.

Misinformation

Misinformation according to Wardle and Derekhshan (2017) is information that is false, but is not created to cause harm. While it is not created to cause harm, the consequences can only be determined by the recipient who may be emotionally affected in the long run. Santin and Pra (2021) opined that in the face of the different sources of information that are present in everyday life, because of constant technological evolutions, it is possible to see the production and distribution of different kind of information and content in accelerated manner, which makes it increasingly difficult to identify sources and to filter the messages received through the different media platforms..

Disinformation

Disinformation is information that is false and is deliberately created to cause harm (Wardle & Derekhshan, 2017). European Commission, cited in Colomina, Margalef and Youngs (2021) defined the concept as 'verifiable false or misleading information that is created, presented and disseminated for economic gain or to intentionally deceive the public and may cause public harm. .Disinformation undermines human rights and many elements of good qualities of democracy, but counter-disinformation measures can also have prejudicial impacts on human rights and democracy (Colomina, et. al. 2021).

Mal-information

Mal-information is a little difference from disinformation as is mal-information is information that is based on reality, but is misused to cause harm on innocent individuals or an entire country. Mal-information requires both intention and equivalence and often involves a repurposing of the truth value of information for deceptive ends (Baines & Elliott, 2020). Everybody knows the value of drugs, but prescribing an overdose of whatever kind could harm the patient. That applies to the way information is misapplied to the audience. People must understand the gravity and implication of mal-information and avoid it for the betterment of our society.

Propaganda

Propaganda involves a systematic dissemination of biased information in order to shape public opinion towards a particular agenda. It carefully crafted in form of emotionally charged language, distorted representation of facts, and manipulation of video or images. Propaganda is a popular weapon of political manipulation in this part of the world.

Fake news:

Fake news refers to fabricated or deliberated misleading news story presented as factual information. It mimics the appearance of a legitimate news article, making it extremely difficult for the audience to verify its authenticity.

Rumors and hoaxes

These are largely false and misleading information often conceived and spread by busy bodies whose aim is to cause distractions. Though harmless, but has the capacity to cause distrust and loss of confidence on people. To mislead and cause distrust and loss of confidence on people especially those in authority

Manipulated media

Media content can be distorted easily with the advancement in technology. Content such digital videos, audio recordings and images can be manipulated to look real in order to spread misinformation, create false evidence or discredit individuals.

Conspiracy theories

This involves narratives that attribute significant event to secretive, malicious or hidden group. They rely on speculations and lack credible evidence to whatever they profess. They operate on unfounded claims that often pose a red signal to the sensibilities of all and sundry.

Theoretical and Empirical Studies

As has been noted, information misuse is all about the inappropriate use of information as when initially collected. Basically, it's when data is not used the way it's initially intended to be used (Sai Chavali, 2018). It is evident as a growing issue for concern in this era that people easily believe what they read and listen to in various media channels. Digital platforms of most relevance to the globe includes website such as Google and Yahoo; open social media and micro-blogging sites such as Facebook and Tweeter; shared news websites such as Reddit; photo sharing sites such as Instagram and Snapchat; video sharing sites such as YouTube and close messaging applications such WhatsApp and Facebook Messenger (Johns, 2019). They are veritable social and political tools.

The creators of misinformation as studied in Africa by Cunliffe-Jones (2022) includes; traditional media and politicians, public institutions, business leaders, traditional and religious leaders, special interest groups, offline community networks and ordinary social media users. The implication is that information misuse occurs when people hold incorrect factual beliefs and do so confidently (Jerit & Zhao, 2020). The social, political and cultural beliefs in the global space have helped in this direction. For instance in the Nigerian 2023 general elections, the new media was optimally utilized especially disseminate or receive information concerning the elections. On the other hand, many politicians and other people used those platforms to spread information that lead to crises that resulted loss of lives and wanton destruction of property which would have if not by the grace of God truncated the continued existence of a democracy in

Nigeria. Misguided utterances through those platforms sparked ethnic and tribal chauvinism. Same digital platforms were used to promote religious hegemony by the clergy of the various religious groups in the country. Worse still; the electoral umpire in the country the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) who also utilized the same platforms assuring Nigerians of free and fair elections (International Crisis Group, 2023). However, the outcome of the elections was flawed by not keeping to the terms of the electoral Act, in which case INEC failed to upload the presidential election results electronically as promised and this did not go down well with Nigerians as it sparked media outrage.

In fact, information misuse is a wind that blows no one any good. In the first instance, it leads to erosion of trust among the people. When people are constantly exposed to misinformation or disinformation, they become skeptical about the information emanating from their leaders. Using Nigeria as a case in point since 1999, Nigerian politicians have been recycling political agenda to the point that an ordinary Nigerian knows exactly what the politicians would promise in the next political campaigns and this has resulted to the citizenry not have any atom of trust on them..

Besides, information misuse has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public; weaken democratic established institutions, polarize the society, suppression of minority groups in the country's freedom of expression would be threatened with continued misinformation and inhibit policy-making.

Inasmuch as rights and powers mean access to data. In the contrary, sometimes for instance, when an employee feels a lack of control, they can use the data they've been given access to for their own benefit. This misuse can threaten an organization's data security or even lead to a data breach. Data misuse was in the top seven categories of threat actions in 2020 according to the Verizon 2021 Data Breach Investigations Report (DBIR). For organizations, data misuse may lead to costly lawsuits and loss of reputation.

The Research Institute of the Nationwide Children's Hospital in Columbus, Ohio, experienced a trade secrets leak that came to light in spring 2021. A researcher at the institute, together with his wife, sold the hospital's trade secrets to China. During ten years of research, the pair collected data in separate laboratories and then illegally handed it to competitors. The secret data, related

to exosomes, is important for research, as well as for identifying and treating various diseases (ABC News, 2021).

For conspiring and selling trade secrets, Yu Zhou, the researcher, was sentenced to 33 months in prison along with confiscation of assets and a \$2.6 million fine.

Cincinnati experienced an abuse of data in February 2020, when sensitive information was misused by a group of employees. They leaked social security and account numbers, driver's licenses, address information, and even customers' mothers' maiden names. As part of a fraud ring, the employees presumably wanted to set up credit accounts outside of Cincinnati, where fraudulent charges would be difficult to catch until reported to credit reporting agencies. After the incident, employees that abused their access to the bank's assets were put under criminal investigation. In turn, the bank took steps to strengthen the security of customers' accounts (Cincinnati, 2020).

For instance In February 2022 revealed Reuter (2022) Credit Suisse suffered an insider attack carried out by an employee whistleblower. The employee leaked data to which he had access to a German newspaper. As a result, information on more than 18,000 accounts (which contained more than \$100 billion) was revealed to the Süddeutsche Zeitung newspaper, and afterwards to a wide number of other global media and organizations. Journalists quickly spread the information, as it contained data on "dirty billings" belonging to some people under sanctions. Shares of Credit Suisse lost around 3% after the incident.

Likewise, on June 26, 2020, a U.S. District Court found Chinese citizen Hao Zhang guilty of trade secrets theft and economic espionage against both Avago and Skyworks. According to the court, Hao collected materials for five years with the aim of helping the Chinese government and opening his own business. Hao and his accomplices obtained information regarding the manufacturing and performance of wireless devices. The conspirators then opened their own company and tried to compete with the firms from which they stole data. Employees of the Chinese Tianjin University also took part in the scheme. (US Ministry of Justice, 2020)

While data misuse can remain unnoticeable for a long time, its consequences can bring lots of harm to an organization individuals and the society at large. In Nigeria for instance, the twists and turns of

politics torch on religious, tribal and cultural believes of the people, especially in Nigeria. Exploring such avenues, politicians and their supporters use religion and tribal sentiments to stir up violence around the country.. Although violence has always been part of the electioneering in this part of the globe, this time around it towed the tribal and religious dimension fueled by information misuse. To this end, it is very important for people to think critically, verify carefully and be careful about the information they consume or use in order to ameliorate the spread of information misuse.

On why information is misused by some people, in a democratic society, one thing stands distinct among politicians- interest! In this clime, most politicians work hard to ensure the protection of their interest even to the detriment of the citizens. Information misuse are motivated by political gains or interest and are facilitated by the media into the itching ears of the audience who gulp this type of information hook, line and sinker without proper verification. According to Lewis and Marwick (2017) research has identified a variety of motivations behind disinformation to financial or political interests, state actors' agenda, trolling and disruption along with even the desire for fame. Other reasons include: gaining political advantage; malicious intent to cause crisis, gaining popularity, destruction of political or democratic structure and creating avenue for personal economic gain.

As has been noted, powerful new technology makes the manipulation and fabrication of content simple and social networks dramatically amplify falsehood peddled by states, populist politicians and dishonest corporate entities as they are shared by uncritical publics (Ireton & Posetti, 2018). This is in line with Butcher (2019) who affirmed that online disinformation is deliberately false or misleading material, often masquerading as news content, which is designed to attract attention and exert influence through online channels.

Contributing on the pros and cons of new media, James Curran and Jean Seaton (2003), posit that two perspectives dominate the debate about the new media in Britain: the neophilic perspective and the cultural pessimist perspective. As explained, they each have opposing views on new media and its advantages and disadvantages. The Neophiliacs or cultural optimists argue that new media is advantageous to society for several reasons. These include: enhancement of

access to information and easy to access a wide range of information on practically every topic, from everyday issues to academic research. People can find information online regardless of their location and often for free, meaning new media is a very valuable resource. New networks and connections through which the global internet makes it easier for individuals to make connections that wouldn't be possible at the local level or through traditional (old) media. Social media also make it easier than ever for people to stay in contact with their loved ones anywhere in the world, not just through messaging but by video calling, playing games together, etc and the revitalizing of democracy that the internet has now become a source of political education and information. This can encourage citizens to play an active role in democratic societies and can make politicians more accountable to the public.

Furthermore, new media has led to cultural globalization in that we can now interact with others on a global level and form connections virtually, rather than locally. These wider networks enable 'collective intelligence' in that they allow people to share and combine resources, data, skills, and information for any given purpose. New media presents a very different reality than our everyday, face-to-face reality - a virtual environment constructed with computer graphics and digital video. Simulations surpass the virtual nature of new media and create an immersive, artificial "life". This is most obvious in computer games which provide opportunities for users to experience a "virtual life" that is simulated through digital (StudySmarter, 2023)

On the other hand, the cultural pessimists believe that the revolution in new media technologies has been exaggerated by neophiliacs and argued among other things that what is primarily new about new media is its speed, the commercialization of the internet has caused considerable privacy concerns. Many companies that sell products and services on the internet now also sell their customers' data by engaging in consumer surveillance. and that new digital technologies, for instance,. in the form of cookies, can track and monitor data generated by users to further target potential audiences, thereby enhancing the company's profits (Comford and Robins, 1999; Hill and Hughes, 1998 ; Curran, 2002),

In the same vain David Harvey suggests that while digital television has drastically increased the number of channels, it has also led to a dumping down of popular culture. The hundreds of channels are filled with generic, cheaply produced material, including repeats and reality TV,

which constitutes a candy-floss culture devoid of creativity or uniqueness. According to Andrew (2007), the democratized nature of the internet can harm the quality of media content. For instance, Wikipedia, a public-produced website, can sometimes be filled with poorly written, uninformed, or false information.

On the roles of libraries and librarians in curbing information misappropriation or misuse, the obvious, is that the exponential growth of information fuelled by the exploitation of media such as the web and social networking, demands that there be a mediator with the skills and capacity to extract trusted and authentic information. Such an intermediary also has to be able to deliver reliable and authoritative information to the information-seeking community as well as the new knowledge and information that has been created in recent times (Tise, 2011). It is this new knowledge and information that help to stimulate the growth and development of societies and the world. Libraries as primary gateways to information are therefore important vehicles for the acquisition of knowledge. As knowledge institutions, libraries provide spaces for information-sharing and learning for all ages, genders, ethnicities and socio-economic groups regardless of their information/knowledge needs (Onwubiko, 2020)

While Nwajiuba (2019), in the context of the African Union (AU) Agenda 2063 and the Charter for African Cultural Renaissance at the 3rd Ministerial Roundtable on Information Access declared, I believe the success of every educational institution depends on its library as the availability of the right information at the right time and form is of utmost importance to users and an improvement of our library systems and access to information/knowledge will bring about social and human capital development. IFLA (2019) in her description of 3rd Roundtable of Ministers Responsible for Public Libraries in Africa held in Accra, Ghana from 28 – 30 October, aimed at improving information access and library systems corroborated the above assertion as it posits that Africa is faced with some of the world's most acute development challenges and needs to draw on all of its innovative potential. Information and equitable access to it IFLA declared will play a key role in achieving this,

Furtherance, libraries as social institutions for creativity, learning, research and leisure, the cardinal responsibility of librarians is to make available the right information and teach how to

access them. As reported by Cunliffe-Jones, et al. (2021), media literacy, even in the broadest sense, was barely taught in six out of the seven countries they studied in June 2020 and no form of misinformation literacy was taught at all except in one province in South Africa. In the Library Schools, information literacy skills are taught and that places the librarians at a vantage point to assist other users. Therefore, below are some of the activities librarians do to curb information misuse..

Furthermore, libraries facilitate access to information thereby providing the means through which new knowledge is developed and made available to all. Knowledge is foundational to all spheres of life. An interrogation of this concept reveals that knowledge is critical for the growth of society and that knowledge is produced when information is absorbed, processed and internalized by individuals (McCallum, 2013). Libraries, as critical providers of information have an important role to play in the creation of new knowledge. They are vital institutions for the creation, development and sustainability of knowledge societies. Information is a key input into the creation and maturation of knowledge, therefore, a significant criterion for a growing and healthy society is access to information. The library, as a major source for/conduit to information, serves a wide spectrum of information-seekers. Libraries are not only vital but also central to the facilitation of knowledge generation.. In the words of Ukoha (2013), Libraries remain portals of knowledge for everyone and they guarantee that whoever you are you can open the door to information, knowledge, learning and help.

To Vrane and markovic (2015), libraries have always been educational, cultural and spiritual centres, places where people had access to relevant knowledge and information. These institutions invest greatly into the intellectual development of their users and contribute to the development of overall democracy of knowledge. They maintain that Librarians are intermediaries between library users and the knowledge whether in printed or digital form.

According to witek (2014), Librarians are not only knowledge creators but knowledge providers. He explains that historically, libraries and librarians are perceived as primary conduits for accessing knowledge as librarians provide knowledge to those who seek it through classification schema, bibliographic instruction, and purchase or license of scholarly materials.

Other roles highlighted to be played by libraries and librarians are: involving in citizens' enlightenment and engagement which can be achieved by the organizing seminars, symposium, and conferences through physical meetings, webinars, Zoom, Google classroom or Skype; Digital literacy and online safety training as well will help those who are not digital natives to approach online content with much understanding, .Fact-checking techniques on the sources of information as to knowing their previous activities,. Collaboration with professional fact checking organisation such as Africa Check, Dubawa and FactCheckHub, Collaboration with other institution, Packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use and Checking and encouraging ethical use of information (Technopedia, 2018; Mavridis, 2019).

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The study applied descriptive survey research design which according to Nworgu (2015) is a type of study which aims at collecting data on and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics features and facts about a given population. This type of study is only interested in describing certain variables like dependent and independent variables in relation to the population.

3.2 Sampled population

The sampled population for this study was 420 selected through purposive sampling technique from the stratified libraries in Nigeria with the exception of the school librarians since no primary or secondary school in Nigeria can boast of a certified librarians. The sampled librarians were identified and selected with the help of Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria list of certified librarians in Nigeria as at 2022. The breakdown shows that academic libraries form 274 of the respondents; public libraries -111, special libraries -20 and national library-15 respondents

3.3 Instrument for data collection and analysis

The primary instrument used in this study for data collection is the questionnaire structured according to the modified Likert scale on four point rating scale. On this scale, the average mean cut off is 2.50, in which case, an item is accepted if it is 2.50 and above and rejected if it is below

2.50 hence the decision rule. The questionnaires were administered through email and returned 93%. The implication is that a total of 450 questionnaires were administered and only 420 were returned. Data collected were statistically analyzed using frequencies and percentile and presented in tables and one chart

4.0: Data Presentation and Analysis

In what Forms are information misuse depicted?

Table 1: Forms of Information Misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Disinformation	200	47.62	76	18.1	46	10.95	98	23.33
Misinformation	313	74.52	30	7.14	57	13.57	20	4.76
Mal-information	69	16.43	210	50	71	16.9	50	11.9
Propaganda	37	8.81	203	48.33	100	23.81	80	19.05
Fake news	340	80.95	80	19.05	-	-	-	-
Rumors and hoaxes	270	64.29	67	15.95	-	-	83	19.76
Manipulated media	32	7.62	233	55.48	-		155	36.9
Conspiracy theories	37	8.81	212	50.48	60	14.29	111	26.43

Key: SA=Strongly Agreed, A=Agreed, DA=Disagreed, SDA=Strongly Disagreed

Figure 1: Forms of information Misuse

The data in table 1 and figure showed that 420 or 100% of the respondents strongly agreed or agreed that information misuse come in the form of fake news, 343 representing 81.67% agreed that it is the form of misinformation, 80.24% of the respondents agreed it in the form of rumors and hoaxed. While, 279 (66.43%) respondents agreed that it come in the form of mal-information, 65.71% or 276 of the 420 respondents agreed that it is in the disinformation, over 50% of the respondents also agreed that information misuse may also be in the form of manipulated media, conspiracy theories and propaganda.

Who are those involved in information misuse?

Table 2: Creators of Information misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%

Traditional Media	188	44.76	112	26.67	70	16.67	50	11.9
Politicians	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
public institutions	198	47.14	76	18.1	62	14.76	84	20
business leaders	120	28.57	160	38.1	60	14.29	80	19.05
traditional and religious leaders,	220	52.38	70	16.67	60	14.29	70	16.67
special interest groups	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
offline community networks	125	29.76	121	28.81	77	18.33	107	25.48
ordinary social media users	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 2 is all about those who are creators of information misuse. The data reveal that the highest peddlers of information misuse are politicians, special interest groups and ordinary social media users with 100% or 420 respondents affirming to that, they were followed by traditional media with 300 or 71.43% affirmative responses while offline community networks took the rear with 246(58.57%) positive responses

What are the Reasons behind information misuse?

Table 3; Reasons for Information Misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Long emotional affection	240	57.14	81	19.29	48	11.43	51	12.14
pose a red signal to the sensibilities of all and sundry	170	40.48	180	42.86	-	-	70	16.67
create false evidence or discredit individuals	220	52.38	101	24.05	50	11.9	11.67	-
To mislead and cause distrust and loss of confidence on people especially those in authority	144	34.29	86	20.48	80	19.05	110	26.19
It mimics the appearance of a legitimate news article, making it extremely difficult for the audience to verify its authenticity	330	78.57	90	21.43	-	-	-	-
to shape public opinion towards a particular agenda	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
to cause harm on innocent individuals or an entire country	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
To create, present and disseminate for economic gain	44	10.48	120	28.57	66	15.71	190	45.24
to intentionally deceive the public and may cause public harm	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Information misuse are motivated by political gains or interest	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Malicious intent to cause crisis	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
For the purpose of gaining popularity	99	23.57	51	12.14	100	23.81	170	40.48

Destruction of political or democratic structure	80	19.05	140	33.33	149	35.48	51	12.14
Creating avenue for personal economic gain	98	23.33	132	31.43	77	18.33	113	26.9

The data in table 3 displayed the indicated reasons why people get involved in information misuse. The data showed that 420 respondents representing 100% strongly agreed that the reasons for information misuse are; to shape public opinion towards a particular agenda; to cause harm on innocent individuals or an entire country, to intentionally deceive the public and may cause public harm, for motivated by political gains or interest and malicious intent to cause crisis. The same 100% strongly agreed or agreed that it is to mimic the appearance of a legitimate news article, making it extremely difficult for the audience to verify its authenticity, while 350 or 83.33% agreed it is to pose a red signal to the sensibilities of all and sundry and 321 representing 76.43% strongly agreed or agreed that it is to create long emotional affection

What new media are used to peddle misinformation?

Table 4; New Media used for Information Misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Radio	54	12.86	16	3.81	100	23.81	160	38.1
Digital Television	80	19.05	20	4.76	220	52.38	100	23.81
Twitter	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Instagram	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Linkidin	-	-	-	-	330	78.57	90	21.43
Facebook Messenger	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
YouTube	290	69.05	55	13.1	30	7.14	45	10.71
WhatsApp	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
SnapChat	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Close Messaging Applications	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
blogs	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Google	23	5.48	77	18.33	98	23.33	222	52.86
Yahoo	320	76.19	12	2.86	98	23.33	-	-
TikTok	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4 presents data collected in respect of the new media in use for information misuse or misinformation. The data revealed the entire 420 respondents representing 100% strongly agreed that Twitter; Instagram, Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, Snapchat, Close Messaging Application, Blogs and TikTok are highly in use for information misuse while 345 of the

respondents representing 82.14% agreed that YouTube is also highly used among other indicated new media..

What are the Consequences of information misuse?

Table 5: Consequences of Information Misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Leads to erosion of trust among the people.	370	88.1	50	11.9				
has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public	411	97.86	09	2.14				
can weaken democratic established institutions	84	20	202	48.1	54	12.86	80	19.05
can polarize the society	391	93.1	29	6.9	-	-	-	-
it could also lead to suppression of minority groups in the country	420	100						
freedom of expression would be threatened with continued misinformation	320	76.19	50	11.9	10	2.38	40	9.52
can inhibit policy-making	120	28.57	111	26.43	90	21.43	99	23.57

Table 5 contains data on the consequences of information misuse. The data collected reveal that 420 of the respondents or 100% strongly agreed or agreed that information misuse leads to suppression of minority groups in the country, leads to erosion of trust among the people. and has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public, 370 or 88.1% strongly agreed or agreed that information misuse is a threat to freedom of expression and 286 or 68.1% agreed it can weaken democratic established institutions

What Roles are Libraries and Librarians expected to play in the fight against information misuse?

Table 6: Roles of Libraries and Librarians

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Libraries and librarians should provide enlightenment to the teaming unsuspecting Nigerians that are always falling prey to the web of misinformation and disinformation	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Librarian should educate the public on how to identify legitimate sites and also to provide guidance on privacy protection, online security, and ability of the users to identify potential risks associated with sharing personal information online.	420	100						

Assume the full position of information mediators	390	92.86	30	7.14				
Fact-checking techniques on the sources of information	420	100						
Collaboration with professional fact checking organisation	264	62.86	86	20.48	34	8.1	46	10.95
. Packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use	217	51.67	203	48.33	-	-	-	-
Checking and encouraging ethical use of information	303	72.14	98	23.33	5	1.19	14	3.33
Collaboration with other institutions	240	57.14	180	42.86	-	-	-	-

The data in table 6 are the perceived roles of libraries and librarians in the fight against information misuse. As shown in the table the entire 420 respondents or 100% strongly agreed that libraries and librarians should provide enlightenment to the teeming unsuspecting Nigerians that are always falling prey to the web of misinformation and disinformation; should educate the public on how to identify legitimate sites and also to provide guidance on privacy protection, online security, and ability of the users to identify potential risks associated with sharing personal information online, Assume the full position of information mediators, and employ fact-checking techniques on the sources of information. The same 100% either strongly agreed or that libraries and librarians should work in collaboration with other institutions and get involved in packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use.

5.0 Discussion of Results

The synthesized data collected as displayed in table 1 and figure 1 did reveal that information misuse is being perpetrated in many forms. The data showed that 420 of the respondents or 100% strongly agreed or agreed that information use come in the form of fake new followed by misinformation with 343 orthen rumor and hoax with% or 337 affirmative responses. Other forms of information misuse affirmed by majority of the respondents as indicated in figure 1 include: disinformation, mal-information, propaganda, conspiracy theories and manipulated media. The outcome of this study is in alliance with the views of Santos-D'amorim and Miranda (2021) who associated misused concepts of misinformation, disinformation and mal-information to words such as; bias, propaganda, retracted papers, conspiracy theories, misleading representation in maps, charts and graphics, fake news, click bait, hoax, satire or parody, imposter website, fake reviews, phishing, filter bubbles, and echo chambers.

The study also discovered as expressed in table 2 and figure 2 where the 420 respondents representing 100% strongly agreed that the persons mostly involved in information misuse are politicians, ordinary social media users and special interest groups. The data also revealed at different proportion but above 60% positive responses that traditional and religious leaders, public institutions, business leaders, and traditional media among others are also involved in information misuse. This result affirms the findings of Cunliffe-Jones (2022) in his study of the creators of misinformation in Africa in which it was discovered that the creators include; traditional media and politicians, public institutions, business leaders, traditional and religious leaders, special interest groups, offline community networks and ordinary social media users.

The data as analyzed in table 3 reveals that the 420 respondents or 100% strongly agreed or agreed that new media such as Tweeter, Facebook Messenger; Instagram, WhatApps, Snapshot, TikTok, Yahoo Messenger, Close Messaging Applications and Blogs are channels mostly used by those creators of misinformation or information misuse. Other media in use to certain degrees include; Google, digital televisions and radio. This finding further buttress the assertion that this powerful new technology makes the manipulation and fabrication of content simple and social networks dramatically amplify falsehood peddled by states, populist politicians and dishonest corporate entities as they are shared by uncritical publics (Ireton & Posetti, 2018). This is also in line with Butcher (2019) who affirmed that online disinformation is deliberately false or misleading material, often masquerading as news content, which is designed to attract attention and exert influence through online channels.

The data collected as displayed in table 4 and figure 4 indicate that 100% or the 420 respondents agreed that main reason behind information misuse are to shape public opinion towards a particular agenda; to cause harm on innocent individuals or an entire country, to intentionally deceive the public and may cause public harm, Information misuse are motivated by political gains or interest and Malicious intent to cause crisis. Other reasons that crossed the benchmark-2,50 or above 60% for which misinformation peddlers indulge in them include; to mimic the appearance of a legitimate news article, making it extremely difficult for the audience to verify its authenticity, Destruction of political or democratic structure; Creating avenue for personal economic gain, To mislead and cause distrust and loss of confidence on people especially those

in authority, create false evidence or discredit individuals, pose a red signal to the sensibilities of all and sundry and Long emotional affection. This finding is consistent with Lewis and Marwick (2017) research that identified a variety of motivations behind disinformation to financial or political interests, state actors' agenda, trolling and disruption along with even the desire for fame. Other reasons include: gaining political advantage; malicious intent to cause crisis, gaining popularity, destruction of political or democratic structure and creating avenue for personal economic gain. This development is far from the purpose of information which is originally meant to enlighten and to dispel ignorance leading to well mannered and well behaved society has been bastardized and now being used as a weapon of mass destruction in our society (Cunliffe-Jones, et al. 2021)..

Table 5 contains data that did reveal that the consequences of information misuse are enormous. According to the data collected, information misuse has so many negative effects on the society which include: it could also lead to suppression of minority groups in the country; has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public, can polarize the society, leads to erosion of trust among the people and can weaken democratic established institutions among others. This discovering is a affirmation of the view expressed that by misrepresenting reality with traces of truth, there is a distortion of entire collective imaginary and manipulation of public opinion which in turn leads to major problems politically, socially and economically (Satin & Pra, 2021)..The above view was also buttressed by Verizon (2021) and Reuter (2022) in their separate reports.

The data in table 6 highlighted the perceived roles of libraries as social institution and librarians as information managers in the fight against information misuse. These roles among many others are; Libraries and librarians should provide enlightenment to the teeming unsuspecting Nigerians that are always falling prey to the web of misinformation and disinformation; Librarian should educate the public on how to identify legitimate sites and also to provide guidance on privacy protection, online security, and ability of the users to identify potential risks

associated with sharing personal information online, Assume the full position of information mediators, Packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use and Collaboration with other institutions.

This result is in conformity with the assertion that Libraries as primary gateways to information are therefore important vehicles for the acquisition of knowledge. As knowledge institutions, libraries provide spaces for information-sharing and learning for all ages, genders, ethnicities and socio-economic groups regardless of their information/knowledge needs (Onwubiko, 2020). It is also in tandem with the views expressed by Technopedia (2018) and Mavridis (2019) that libraries and librarians should be involved in citizens' enlightenment and engagement through the organizations of seminars, symposium, and conferences, physical meetings, webinars, Zoom, Google classroom or Skype and also conduct digital literacy and online safety training through which those who are not digital natives are can be helped to approach online content with much understanding, .As well as applying Fact-checking techniques on the sources of information as to knowing their previous activities and collaborating with professional fact checking organisation such as Africa Check, Dubawa and FactCheckHub.

5.1. Conclusion and Recommendations

The outcome of this study has actually shown that information misuse which may be in the form of misinformation, mal-information, propaganda, fake new, rumor and hoax, manipulated media or conspiracy theories are mostly created by politicians, traditional leaders, business leaders, individual users of social media among others using various new media for propagation. The result also discovered that those involved in information misuse apply them for their own selfish end at the detriment of the wider society. Generally, the outcome of this study has exposed the fact that information misuse is a hydra-headed monster which if not checked can sink our society. While the new media stands as a double edge sword with the first edge representing initial intention of enhancement of access to information and easy to access a wide range of information on practically every topic, from everyday issues to academic research. Besides,

people can find information online regardless of their location and often for free, meaning new media is a very valuable resource and the second the awkward application in which the **new** technology has made the manipulation and fabrication of content simple and social networks dramatically amplifying falsehood. To this end, it was discovered that librarians and libraries have prominent roles to play in fight this anti-social act (see table 6) The implication is that librarians are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that the right information goes out and wrong ones countered. The people need to know how to fact-check information before sharing. People should be enlightened on the appropriate channels to access information, because even the conventional information channels are faced with menace of misinformation and disinformation. Libraries as credible and reputable social institutions whose contents are not in doubt should therefore champion the course of dispelling information misuse in our society. In accordance with findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. In the first instance, libraries and Librarians should occupy the drivers' seats as information mediators and directors with a view to winning public confidence through the provision and dissemination of accurate and reliable information.
2. Public libraries which is so to speak the people's universities should be built in every part of a country to enable the citizens to have access to the right information always with each installed with 'user monitoring solution'. One of the best ways to detect and prevent data misuse is to see exactly what happens after data is accessed. A dedicated user monitoring solution allows you to easily see what has happened with data when it was used, how and by whom.
3. Libraries' management should as a matter of necessity train every staff on cyber and data security as a general corporate policy. A well-thought-out policy is a reliable source of information about in-house procedures and standards.

4. Library schools should set up educational courses on data security. A generic course on cyber-security is always useful to remind staff not to share their credentials, inform them about new phishing methods, among others. Librarians should be well informed on why it's important to take care of sensitive data and what consequences data misuse will have not only for the library and themselves but also for the society at large. This to say, that library staffs should be up to speed with technology and use their social media handles to disseminate reliable information and to also counter misused information in the media.
5. Information misuse as a crime against the society should be considered a serious offence, there countries should enact stringent laws that will make offenders/perpetrators pay dearly for it as to serve as deterrent to others who may be having the intention to indulge in such act.
6. New media, particularly the internet, should be regulated by the state. Since all views, opinions and content can be freely expressed and accessed on the internet; measures should be taken to combat potentially harmful content e.g. homophobic, racist and terrorism-inciting comments and websites. To breathe easy, libraries should not only secure all their data at rest and in transit but also wisely configure notifications and provide courses to support their staff members. This implies that Social media website owners should properly monitor the kinds of information being circulated to the public and should be ready to take down any information that is capable of causing problem in the society.

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